

POWER EFFICIENT 16-T HYBRID FULL ADDER FOR PORTABLE APPLICATIONS

Dharani.M (II M.E VLSI Design, Akshaya college of Engineering and Technology,)

Nimisha.K (Assistant Professor (Senior Grade), ECE department, Akshaya College of Engineering and Technology,)

M.E VLSI Design, Anna University

Abstract

The Full Adder (FA) circuit designed with different methodologies forming a hybrid logic configuration is proposed. The foremost oddity of these hybrid methodology based full adder is to effectively utilize the advantageous feature of different logic style incorporated in a single design. Such a power optimized 1-bit hybrid FA cell is proposed with pass transistor logic, transmission gate logic and gate diffusion input technique. The hybrid combination results in reduction of total transistor count without performance degradation, due to the usage of different logic style at required positions. The proposed FA circuit is implemented using 16-transistors to achieve optimum performance. The proposed circuit is designed using DSCH2 and simulated in Microwind tool by using various CMOS technology. Comparison of the design metrics for the proposed 1-bit hybrid FA cell against the existing FA circuits is also carried out. The evaluation result shows that present study reported 71.9% power reduction in an average when applied to 90nm, 65nm and 45nm CMOS technologies. Furthermore, the FA circuit is verified for higher order bit length extending up to 128-bits which is suitable in various arithmetic applications.

Keywords—Full adder, transmission gate, gate diffusion input, pass transistor, hybrid logic style.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the technology scaling continuous to happen, a need for effective design satisfying low power consumption and higher performance becomes very much essential. Full adders, generally used as a fundamental block in various portable applications such as microprocessor, IoT devices, signal and image processing applications need to be efficiently design. Because it acts as a core unit, used repeatedly to construct larger bit adders and multipliers. Full adder is used in larger numbers for partial product addition of multiplier and also in the comparator unit. So, any efficient design of 1-bit full adder has a high potential impact in various arithmetic applications [1]-[2].

Various static and dynamic design styles are used for constructing arithmetic block. The static methodology uses CMOS design as a basic component for designing the arithmetic block. It is affected with low impedance DC path and needs tri-state buffers for larger circuits. The static design can also be constructed using TTL logic. Dynamic methodology uses clock to drive the combinational logic output which increases the switching speed, but with the cost of additional transistor and power consumption. It needs a power gating techniques to keep the transition minimum during idle state [3]-[5]. Another solution in improving the static design is replacing the conventional CMOS with hybrid logic style to achieve area-delay-power tradeoffs.

The CMOS uses PMOS and NMOS transistor producing full voltage swing and can effectively deal with transistor sizing, but is largely affected with negative bias temperature instability. Another methodology used in literatures for designing is the use of complementary and differential Pass Transistor Logic (PTL). It has higher driving capabilities, but its disadvantages lies in complex physical design and more power consumption. Another way to realize the adder circuit is by using pass transistor method, which requires minimum number of transistors with poor driving capabilities. Transmission Gate (TG) design is incorporated to it to achieve stability, but still has a poor performance compared to conventional designs [6]-[9]. Gate Diffusion Input (GDI) technique is another way to design basic blocks by low complexity which uses all the three terminals as input and output. Separately designed GDI architecture results in producing weak output signal [10].

Hybrid logic style acts as an effective design methodology to overcome the drawbacks of individual methods by combining its advantageous features [11]-[14]. The main challenge in hybrid design is selection of various designs at necessary nodes for achieving the optimum result. The rest of the proposed article is ordered as follows. Section II gives the literature survey on various individual and hybrid logic style methodologies. Section III briefs about different logic styles. Section IV proposed a novel hybrid methodology to construct a full adder. Section V evaluates the result of the proposed design and it is compared with the existing methods. The paper is finally concluded in section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Jyoti Kandpal, Abhishek Tomar and Mayur Agarwal (2021) in the paper “Design and implementation of 20-T hybrid full adder for high-performance arithmetic applications” described hybrid design of full adder by using three different style of logic. The idea behind it is to extract the required optimized part from CMOS, transmission gate and pass transistor logic. The total number of transistor used for designing 1-bit adder is 20 and is designed using 90nm technology. The basic XOR and XNOR designs require for full adder is constructed using pass transistor logic. The remaining sum and carry block are designed using combination of pass transistor and transmission gates. Minimal power consumption and lesser delay is achieved using this technique [2].

J. Kandpal, A. Tomar, M. Agarwal and K.K. Sharma (2020) in the paper “High-speed hybrid-logic full adder using high- performance 10-T XOR–XNOR cell” described another hybrid form to design 1-bit full adder. XOR–XNOR is a predominant structure in a full adder and it is focused in this article. It is designed using 10-T circuit design improving the driving capability and resulting in full swing output. It is designed using 90-nm technology and achieves 7.5% minimal power-delay product compared with existing XOR–XNOR modules. The result is also validated for 2-bit, 4-bit and 8-bit designs [6].

J. Kandpal, A. Tomar, K. Pandey and M. Agarwal (2019) in the paper “High performance 20-T based hybrid full adder using 90nm CMOS technology” described a high performance full adder with hybrid methodology. XOR and XNOR outputs are generated simultaneously increasing the performance. The design is constructed by using 90nm technology with 1.2v as the supply voltage. The design resulted in more than 50% delay and PDP improvement and works well for various range of supply voltage [7].

V.R. Tirumalasetty and M.R. Machupalli (2019) in the paper “Design and analysis of low power high-speed 1-bit full adder cells for VLSI applications” pass transistor logic and transmission gate methodology is used for designing the adder to minimize the power consumption and total number of transistor used. The two designs utilize 16 and 14 transistors. At 1.2v supply and 0.18 μm technology the design results in lower delay and PDP. The proposed design is extended for 8-bit adder and its results in lower PDP [8].

P. Bhattacharyya, B. Kundu, S. Ghosh, V. Kumar and A. Dandapat (2015) in the paper “Performance analysis of a Low-Power High-Speed Hybrid 1-bit Full Adder Circuit” are designed using CMOS and transmission gates. It is designed using 180nm and 90nm CMOS technology at 1.8v supply voltage resulting in minimal delay and power consumption. It designed is used to construct a 32-bit adder. The weak CMOS is compensated by transmission gates and pass transistor logic. The hybrid design results in improved driving capability [9].

M. Shoba and R. Nakkeeran (2016) in the paper “GDI based full adders for energy efficient arithmetic applications” described gate diffusion input technique which acts as a methodology for all the building modules of the adder. OR, XOR and AND gates are constructed using GDI results in a weak signal propagation. GDI also is affected with threshold problem when implemented with full swing voltage. It is designed using 45nm technology and results in lower power comparison compared other logic designs [10].

III. DIFFERENT LOGIC FAMILIES

A. Pass Transistor Logic

In order to lower the number of transistors in a circuit design, pass logic using transistors is employed. Transistors function as switches, transferring logical levels '0' and '1' from one node to another. In the pass transistor, the voltage decreases as it passes through the stages, in contrast to standard CMOS design where the voltage varies between V_{dd} and G_{nd} . To increase performance, standard CMOS buffers must accommodate large cascaded circuits.

Fig.1. Pass transistor logic

Fig.1 illustrates an AND gate employing pass transistor logic. B and $\bar{B}$ are fed to two NMOS that are connected in parallel for the respective gate terminal. The source is designated as A, and the connecting node and transistor both provide the output of '0'. A value is regarded the output if B is high; else, "0" is considered the

output. Just two gates are needed in the transistor's pass logic to generate the output. When NMOS reaches zero, it has a stronger driving capability; when it transcends V_{dd} or the source signal, it has a weaker driving capability.

B. Transmission gates

Transistors: 4=2 (transmission gate)+2 (inverter)

Fig.2. Transmission Gates

Transmission gates are a class of logic circuits made consisting of a parallel connection between a PMOS and an NMOS. The gate voltages for these gates (C and Cbar in Fig. 2) are in opposition to one another. Under the guidance of signal C, transmission gates operate as a bidirectional switch between nodes A and B. The gates of NMOS and PMOS are linked to C and Cbar, respectively (invert of C). Both transistors are active and offer a low resistance channel between A and B when the signal controlled by C is high, or V_{DD}. Conversely, both transistors are off when C is low, creating a high impedance route between A and B.

C. Gate Diffusion Input Technique

The VLSI method for lowering static and dynamic power consumption in digital circuits is gate diffusion input. This method allows for the building of a variety of digital circuits with fewer transistors than CMOS designs, which reduces power dissipation. With just two MOS transistors and the Gate Diffusion Input (GDI) approach, a large variety of mixed functions can be implemented. Because the GDI approach uses fewer transistors, it has the advantages of high speed, low power consumption, and low area. As seen in Fig. 3, the Basic Cell of GDI resembles a basic CMOS inverter. The GDI Cell considers G, P, and N as inputs.

- G is the input applied common to the gate terminals of NMOS and PMOS
- N input is applied to source/Drain of NMOS
- P input is applied to the source/drain of PMOS

Fig.3. Basic GDI Cell

Depending on the circuit to be created, the N, P, and G terminals of the GDI method can be connected to a power supply (V_{dd}), grounded, or supplied with an input signal. This effectively reduces the amount of transistors needed in the majority of logic circuits. The "P" or "N" terminals are where bulks of PMOS and NMOS are joined, respectively.

This method can be used to create low-power digital circuits for embedded systems. In comparison to the current standard designs, the circuit uses fewer transistors overall, which reduces both the amount of delay and power consumption. The ability to create a wide range of functionalities is the main advantage of employing the GDI approach. Swing deterioration is the primary disadvantage of the GDI approach. This is caused by threshold loss,

which must be eliminated using the very costly silicon on insulator or twin-well technique. Using the GDI approach, the XOR gate is the main building block for designing a full adder.

IV. PROPOSED 16-T FULL ADDER DESIGN

The primary block diagram of a complete adder employing XOR with a pass transistor and a gate diffusion input technique—which results in the SUM and CARRY blocks—is displayed in Fig.4. Transmission gates, gate diffusion input method, and pass transistor logic are used to form the sum and carry of the full adder. To maximize the circuit's performance in terms of area, latency, and power consumption, each module is constructed separately. Two XOR gates are used to generate the output of the SUM module. The current 20T design's pass transistor logic is used to implement the initial XOR. Using the gate diffusion input approach, the second XOR gate is meant to reduce the overall number of transistors utilized.

The MUX circuits and TG logic are used to implement the carry module. The XOR and XNOR values from the preceding module are used by both transmission gates. One transmission gate is connected to values A and B, while another is connected to value CIN. Together, they produce the carry. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the suggested XOR design is implemented utilizing CPL logic and a single static inverter. The XOR output is realized independently in the circuit that is suggested. The XOR design makes use of two PMOS and two NMOS. Transistors are linked in parallel to form PTL logic at the XOR design. Furthermore, pass transistors are used to implement transistors, in which the source and gate correspond to the inverted input B, respectively.

Fig.4. Proposed 16-T full adder block

Fig.5. XOR gate using PTL

Fig.6. XOR gate using GDI

As seen in Fig. 6, A and B are the inputs of the XOR gate employing GDI. The PMOS and NMOS transistors share gate input A. B is provided, by inversion, to the source of NMOS and directly to the source of PMOS. Based on the input data, the coupled drain terminals of the PMOS and NMOS generate the XOR output. The carry module (COUT), as depicted in Fig. 7, is the third module in the suggested FA circuit. Utilizing MUX circuits and TG logic, this module is implemented. The XOR and XNOR values from the preceding module are used by both transmission gates. One transmission gate is connected to values A and B, while another is connected to value CIN. Together, they produce the carry.

Fig.7. Carry generation block

V. EVALUATION RESULTS

Fig.8. Timing diagram of 16-T full adder

The Fig.8 shows the functional output of the 16-T full adder designed and simulated using DSCH tool. A, B and C are the input signal of the full adder with sum and carry as its output.

Fig.9. Layout of 16-T full adder

The Fig.9 shows the layout of the 16T- hybrid full adder for 90nm technology obtained using Microwind tool.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE of FA CELLS IN 90 NM CMOS TECHNOLOGY at 1.2V SUPPLY VOLTAGE.

DESIGN	TRANSISTOR	DELAY(ns)	POWER(uW)	PDP(fJ)
EXISTING 20T FA	20	1.994	35.344	70.476
PROPOSED 16T FA	16	0.963	9.921	9.554

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE of FA CELLS IN 65 NM CMOS TECHNOLOGY at 0.7V SUPPLY VOLTAGE.

DESIGN	TRANSISTOR	DELAY(ns)	POWER(uW)	PDP(fJ)
EXISTING 20T FA	20	8.000	2.433	19.464
PROPOSED 16T FA	16	2.002	2.203	4.410

Fig. 10. (a)Power (b) Delay (c) PDP results under varying supply voltage.

Table I and Table II represents the performance result of existing and proposed FA structure in terms of delay (input to output), power consumption, and PDP for 90nm and 65nm technology. By optimizing transistors' size, there is a significant reduction in delay along with power consumption. In addition, minimum PDP is also achieved by optimization.

It is apparent from the table that the proposed FA design gives the lowest delay among all reviewed circuits. The proposed design offers a 51.7–74.9% improvement in delay when compared to existing structures. Power reduction also achieved in the range 9.45-71.9% based on the technology and supply voltage. The proposed design results in optimized PDP between 77.3-86.4% compared to the existing design.

Fig. 10(a), the proposed FA design is compared with the reviewed FA circuits based on their power and it is found that the proposed FA cell exhibited the best performance amongst available FA cells as shown in Fig. 10(b). Moreover, the PDP of the proposed FA design showed the best results for different supply voltages, as shown in Fig. 10(c).

VI. CONCLUSION

VLSI designers have the freedom to use several modules to create the circuit based on their requirements when using a hybrid method. A new design for a 1-bit FA using a hybrid design technique and 16 transistors is given in the proposed study. The suggested approach improves driving capabilities and resolves the threshold voltage issue. The current study proposes an outstanding durability 1-bit hybrid FA cell with gate diffusion input technology, pass transistor logic, and transmission gate logic. Because the hybrid combination uses a different logic architecture where it is needed, the total number of transistors is reduced without performance being compromised. The evaluation result from the Microwind tool indicates that, when applied to 90nm, 65nm, and 45nm CMOS technologies, the current study indicated an average power saving of 71.9%. The results show that the suggested design is extremely resilient under all circumstances. The suggested approach is hence appropriate for high-performance VLSI applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.P. Chandrakasan, S. Sheng, R.W. Brodersen, Low-power CMOS digital design, *IEEE J. Solid State Circ.* 27 (1992) 473–483.
- [2] Jyoti Kandpal, Abhishek Tomar, Mayur Agarwal, Design and implementation of 20-T hybrid full adder for high-performance arithmetic applications, *Microelectron. J.* 38 (1) (2021) 105–205, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mejo.2021.105205>.
- [3] M. Zhang, J. Gu, and C.-H. Chang, "A novel hybrid pass logic with static CMOS output drive full-adder cell," in *Proc. Int. Symp. Circuits Syst.*, May 2003, pp. 317–320.
- [4] A. M. Shams, T.K. Darwish, and M. A. Bayoumi, "Performance analysis of low-power 1-bit CMOS full adder cells," *IEEE Trans. Very Large Scale Integr. (VLSI) Syst.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 20–29, Feb. 2002.
- [5] C.-K. Tung, Y.-C. Hung, S.-H. Shieh, and G.-S. Huang, "A low-power high-speed hybrid CMOS full adder for embedded system," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Design Diagnostics Electron. Circuits Syst.*, vol. 13, Apr. 2007, pp. 1–4.
- [6] J. Kandpal, A. Tomar, M. Agarwal, K.K. Sharma, High-speed hybrid-logic full adder using high-performance 10-T XOR–XNOR cell, *IEEE Trans. Very Large Scale Integr. Syst.* 28 (6) (2020) 1413–1422. <https://10.1109/TVLSI.2020.2983850>.
- [7] J. Kandpal, A. Tomar, K. Pandey, M. Agarwal, High performance 20-T based hybrid full adder using 90nm CMOS technology, in: 2019 Women Institute of Technology Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering (WITCON ECE), 2019, pp. 192–195, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WITCONECE48374.2019.9092897>.
- [8] V.R. Tirumalasetty, M.R. Machupalli, Design and analysis of low power high-speed 1-bit full adder cells for VLSI applications, *Int. J. Electron.* 106 (4) (2019) 521–536, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207217.2018.1545256>.
- [9] P. Bhattacharyya, B. Kundu, S. Ghosh, V. Kumar and A. Dandapat, "Performance Analysis of a Low-Power High-Speed Hybrid 1-bit Full Adder Circuit," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 2001–2008, Oct. 2015.
- [10] M. Shoba and R. Nakkeeran, "GDI based full adders for energy efficient arithmetic applications," *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 485–496, 2016.
- [11] F. Frustaci, M. Lanuzza, P. Zicari, S. Perri and P. Corsonello, "Designing High-Speed Adders in Power-Constrained Environments," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 172–176, Feb. 2009.
- [12] A. Pal, *Low Power VLSI Circuits and Systems*, New Delhi, India: Springer India, 2015.
- [13] B. K. Mohanty, "Efficient Fixed-Width Adder-Tree Design," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 66, no. 2, pp. 292–296, Feb. 2019.
- [14] S. Purohit and M. Margala, "Investigating the impact of logic and circuit implementation for full adder performance," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 1327–1331, 2012.